

Ethical Challenges of Transhumanism and Augmentation

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence and Robotics are advancing at a rapid rate. Especially into the areas of health and biotechnology. Not only do they aid research and development, but they are changing our approach to how we solve many of our health problems. Illness and disabilities ranging from missing limbs and damaged spines to Alzheimer's and aging, researchers are using AI and advanced robotics to return people to full human-level functionality. It's a beautiful thing and what technology is best at.

Returning people to human-level functionality is undeniable and undebatable, however it is that natural next steps where we begin to see some tremendous ethical dilemmas and in your speaker's mind, some insurmountable challenges. This talk will define transhumanism, augmentation and the stated goals of many of the leading developers in these field. With that background, we will then examine how these advancements will create problems in society that will require some create and innovative solutions. We will examine a likely increase in income inequality. We will examine the addition of super-human skills and the impact on job competitiveness. We will examine the risks of technology in your body. Finally, we will explore the potential of the world where solutions aren't found and the risk that poses to society in the form of two version of humanity, natural versus augmented and the risk of a divided society.

The talk does not attempt to answer these questions directly, but to raise the awareness of the challenges of transhumanism and augmentation. The talk also does not take a side, but because one of the two sides is distinctly inferior to the other, there is a desire to look out for the weaker side, the natural human.

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Artificial Intelligence, Transhumanism, Augmentation, Ethics

Author biography

Ryan Carrier Mr. Carrier launched ForHumanity in mid 2016, in an attempt to raise awareness of key issues around AI Safety. ForHumanity aims to implement independent third-party auditing of AI & Automation for Security, Safety, Control, Bias, Privacy and Ethics/Standards. Prior to founding ForHumanity, Mr. Carrier spent 23 years on Wall

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Street including time with the World Bank, Standard & Poor's and Macquarie Bank. He founded a hedge fund called Nautical Capital in 2009, which he closed in order to dedicate himself full-time to ForHumanity.

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